

COULD GENERATIVE AI SUPPORT IMPACT-ORIENTED INFORMATION SYSTEM RESEARCH?

Short Paper

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Abstract

Examples in this paper demonstrate the possibility of applying generative AI (GenAI) in impact-oriented IS research. The examples illustrate initial efforts to use GenAI in research that extends the work system perspective (WSP), whose evolution over three decades consistently focused on making it clearer, broader in scope, and more impactful. This paper is organized around the guiding questions in the CFP of the First Impact-oriented Information Systems Workshop. Two figures illustrate WSP's scope and its position at the area of overlap between many disciplines. Recent applications of GenAI are described that aim to increase WSP's impact, ideally for the benefit of organizations and society.

Keywords: Impact-oriented research, Generative AI, Work system theory, Work system perspective

1 Unpacking the Workshop's Title

A great deal is packed into this workshop's title "Visions of Meaning for Impact-Oriented Information Systems Research in Times of Polycrisis: Quo Vadis?" The title implies that impact-oriented IS research (IIS research) somehow differs from other IS research in content or intent. The term "visions of meaning" implies that the idea of "impact-orientation" in IS research is unclear and controversial. "Times of polycrisis" implies that a current polycrisis should affect research topics, goals, and methods.

This paper pursues a somewhat contrarian approach by assuming IS research should be impact-oriented regardless of whether it occurs during a time of polycrisis. It builds on an impact-oriented IS research stream that aims to produce concepts, examples, generalizations, and tools and methods that business and IT professionals can use effectively for describing, analyzing, designing, and improving IT-enabled systems that operate within or across organizations. That research is based on an organized set of ideas for describing work systems at multiple levels of depth. Applying a coherent set of ideas increases the likelihood that GenAI can provide a genuine contribution to developing those ideas further. Ongoing efforts aimed at extending that research stream are definitely impact-oriented even if their goals are not as ambitious as the goal of bettering society and mankind at a time of polycrisis.

This paper's response to the five guiding questions in the CFP uses the first four questions as background for a longer response to Q5 focusing on recent research that uses GenAI to extend a work system perspective that has evolved over three decades and continues to evolve.

Q1 — What does "impact" mean to you? IS research has impact if it affects the thinking, intentions, and actions of business or governmental stakeholders, IS/IT professionals, students, and/or IS researchers. IS research with the highest likelihood of impact occurs when a business or government organization performs that research as part of developing product/services for employees or customers. Research of that type is designed to have impact. Academic research might have impact if it addresses a major knowledge gap or important misunderstanding or if it is directed toward goals or needs of business or government organizations concerning high priority topics such as competitive challenges, internal efficiency, product/service quality, cyber-security, and so on.

Unfortunately, the IS discipline undermines its potential impact when it adopts inward-facing priorities that try to protect its unique identity. An example is a 2003 *CAIS* debate about the core and scope of the

IS field centered on responses by ten *CAIS* editorial board members to issues discussed in two articles related to the core, scope, and identity of the IS field. Benbasat & Zmud's (2003) article "The Identity Crisis Within the IS Discipline: Defining and Communicating the Discipline's Core Properties" argued that IS research should focus on the IT artifact and its immediate nomological network and should reduce the degrees of separation between IS constructs and key constructs in research. My rebuttal was "Sidestepping the IT Artifact, Scrapping the IS Silo, and Laying Claim to 'Systems in Organizations'" (Alter, 2003). Industry experience in a successful manufacturing software company led me to view a restrictive focus as a recipe for reducing impact because the rest of the world does not care about what does and does not qualify as IS research. Years later, the IS field's focus (or obsession or fetish) related to theory led Hirschheim (2019) to warn that the IS discipline's "mindless obedience of making theory the only thing that matters," closes off research that does not fit theory-driven approaches, and leads "down a dangerous path toward irrelevancy." In terms of research practices, inward-facing methods such as literature reviews that mine the Senior Scholars' Basket of Eight omit other knowledge sources that might lead to higher impact. As an example, "work system theory" (first published in 2013) appears 176 times in the AIS eLibrary but has never been mentioned in *MIS Quarterly*.

Q2 — Impact in practice. The stream of research related to the work system perspective (WSP) initially had impact through extensive classroom use of four editions of an introductory IS textbook. During 2003–2017, (mostly) MBA and EMBA students demonstrated the usability of a work system-oriented approach by applying various work system analysis templates in assignments that produced over 700 management briefings about possible improvements in real-world work systems, mostly in their organizations, e.g., Truex et al. (2010). Some MBA and EMBA students described job-related use of ideas they had absorbed from those projects. The 2013 publication of work system theory (WST) and subsequent extensions such as the theory of workarounds have had a degree of impact on academic research, as implied by their explicit use in papers by authors around the world. In general I think that a realistic path toward greater impact on practice calls for developing ideas that help business and IT professionals understand system-related challenges that they face.

Q3 — Meaningful vs. impactful research. Ideally IS research also should have a plausible possibility of providing significant benefits for others. In my case, the long-term goal has been developing organized and internally consistent ideas that business and IT professionals can use effectively for describing, analyzing, designing, and improving IT-enabled systems that operate within or across organizations. That research has been meaningful to me even without highly visible impact on society.

Q4 — Researching in times of polycrisis. It is unrealistic for most IS research to aspire to significant impact on business or society, especially since few non-researchers ever see IS research articles, as has been discussed repeatedly. Also, the possibility of research impact is strongly related to social networks within and between academic disciplines. Single publications or isolated research efforts rarely generate highly visible near-term impact (see related discussion in Kuhn, 1997).

Q5 — Generative AI and the future of impactful research. The widespread adoption of GenAI in the last several years provides many directions for research with significant impacts on productivity, employment, education, and career advancement. Examples include research about uses of GenAI for consulting work (Dell'Acqua et al., 2026), uses in customer service (Brynjolfsson et al., 2025), uses in coding (Liu et al., 2023), and other recent papers. Those are examples of behavioral research about the use of GenAI. In contrast, most of my GenAI-related research uses it as a tool to apply or extend WSP. Examples of that research will be presented after brief background about WST/WSP ideas.

2 Work System Perspective

Examples in the next section focus on applications of GenAI to various aspects of the work system perspective (WSP), whose core is work system theory (WST) as shown in Figure 1. A long stream of papers published before the availability of GenAI were devoted to many of the WST/WSP topics and relationships in Figure 1, such as the work system method, ISs as work systems, the work system life cycle model, a service value chain framework, theory of workarounds, facets of work, IS usage theory,

3 Exploratory Applications of GenAI that Might Lead to Impact

This section discusses exploratory GenAI-based projects whose results suggest possibilities for future WSP extensions, which could lead to meaningful impact in the future. All of the GenAI applications described here involve using GenAI to test existing ideas or develop new ideas. The first example (3.1) provided case studies for the second (3.2), which is this research stream's most advanced application to date. The other examples point in other directions that might prove fruitful.

(3.1) Producing synthetic case studies for theory building, method evaluation, and educational purposes. Possible uses of synthetic case studies produced by LLMs include theory building, method evaluation, and coursework usage for assignments and student evaluation. Example 3.2 required a set of comparable IS case studies. An LLM was used to create 11 synthetic cases of around 1,500 words based on brief situation descriptions of around 175 words. Six of the brief descriptions were based on longer cases in a 2021 BPM case book. Five were based on personal knowledge of other situations. Here is the beginning of a typical prompt requesting a synthetic case study: *Produce a case study of around 1,500 words related to major business processes in firm M6, a manufacturing company specializing in the production of small mechanical parts using additive manufacturing (3D printing) technologies. It serves industrial customers in aerospace, medical devices, robotics, and specialized equipment repair. M6 operates from a single production facility and handles a mix of repetitive and custom one-time orders. Its customer base is primarily regional, although*

(3.2) Identifying foreseeable workarounds during systems analysis and design. Workarounds are ubiquitous in organizations because nontrivial sociotechnical systems typically need to combine codified regularity with some amount of flexibility for responding to situations that require judgment-based deviation from standard practices. LLMs provide a possible path for identifying foreseeable workarounds, thereby helping designers and managers decide what to do about foreseeable workarounds that are potentially beneficial or likely harmful. Alter (2026b) explains how the four-step process below created and justified a useful set of 83 generic workarounds, each categorized under one of the nine elements of the work system framework. That set of generic workarounds could be incorporated into checklists or tools to help in visualizing foreseeable workarounds before implementation:

- 1) Identify 50 foreseeable workarounds for each of 10 synthetic case studies and organize those workarounds using the nine elements of the work system framework.
- 2) Use an LLM to produce a list of broadly applicable generic workarounds by eliminating situation-specific details from each of the 500 workarounds identified in Step 1.
- 3) Produce a single organized list of generic workarounds by combining the ten lists and removing or combining near duplicates, resulting in a set of generic workarounds in nine categories that might help in reviewing a new system before implementation.
- 4) Demonstrate potential usefulness by having an LLM use generic workarounds from Step 3 to identify foreseeable situation-specific workarounds in a different case study.

The paper was rejected by the CAISE 2026 conference, with one review saying it was fascinating and creative but had to be rejected because it raises "so many questions concerning methodology that I don't even know where to start. Is this even close to an acceptable method? If not, is it by itself still a valuable contribution?" Since the rejection arrived one week before the due date for EMMSAD, a large pre-CAISE workshop, I added a minor revision that addressed the methodology question and the paper was accepted. The revision stated that the research used a new method that might be called GARCA: generative abstraction, refinement, compilation, and application. Variations on that type of GenAI application might be used in other research efforts that try to produce or test reusable knowledge.

Naming the method GARCA was basically a workaround aimed at accommodating the common belief that research needs to use an identifiable methodology. I do not want to belittle the thoughtful CAISE review that led to the workaround. It identified issues about using GenAI as a tool in research (beyond simply performing compilations or editing or summarizing papers after the research is done). More broadly, those issues concern replicability when using GenAI and how to justify results produced by research with significant direct or indirect assistance from GenAI.

(3.3) Preliminary analysis of case studies using theories and other generalizations. As noted earlier, MBA and EMBA students used work system outlines for producing over 700 management briefings. The availability of LLMs led to wondering whether an LLM could produce similar briefings. Alter (2024) pursued that challenge through a quasi-experiment in which three different ChatGPT-4 prompts (for system structure, analysis, and recommendations) were applied in standard or augmented form to each of three case studies (automated warehouses, ride hailing platforms, and medication administration systems). The augmented forms (treatments) were based on different sets of ideas. Each case study comprised 3,000+ words. The prompts were detailed requests for responses of up to 500 words related to three steps (system structure, analysis, and recommendations) related to those cases. A null treatment serving as a quasi-control used standard prompts for each case without augmentation. The first actual treatment was a simplification of a work system analysis template used by MBA and EMBA students; the other six were sets of questions based on activity theory, a BPM design space, work system principles, and three other identifiable sets of ideas. The research questions were whether ChatGPT-4 could produce a useful first cut at system structure, analysis, and recommendations and whether various augmentations of ChatGPT-4 prompts improve or extend the outputs significantly. Most of the responses for structure and analysis were reasonably good across the various treatments, but many of the recommendations were impractical because LLMs do not understand contexts.

(3.4) GenAI-assisted theorizing and identification of risk factors. An exploratory paper (Alter, 2025b) pursued a new direction in the long stream of IS usage research. The paper's first section used ChatGPT-4o in a four-phase "refining" process to create 125 sentences in each of four broad categories (favoring or inhibiting IT adoption and usage and favoring or inhibiting IS success) and to reduce those to 25 sentences in each category, then 10 sentences in each category, and finally a reduced set of 10 sentences describing factors that seem most important for IS/IT adoption, use, and success. That result might be considered a highly debatable draft of a new theory of IS/IT adoption, use, and success. The second section extended that general approach by using five different LLMs to produce organized lists of success factors for IS usage. Each of the five LLMs responded to the same four prompts that requested increasing degrees of specificity in those success factors. An additional prompt instructed each LLM to refine results from the other four LLMs down to a new list of 15 or more success factors for IS usage. It is unclear how to assess whether those results should be viewed as a contribution to knowledge.

(3.5) Testing the value of work system axioms. Alter (2025a) tested the value of 24 work system axioms by using GenAI to apply one question implied by each axiom to two real-world case studies. Most of the answers were potentially useful for describing and analyzing those systems. A much longer paper that looked at the axioms in depth and explained more about their application to the two case studies was rejected by two leading journals, in one case partially because the axioms seemed obvious (as axioms tend to be) and because the axioms did not qualify as a theory.

(3.6) Comparing alternative theories. Alter (2026a) tested Lewin's often repeated aphorism that nothing is as practical as a good theory by comparing the usefulness of three LLM-generated sets of 10 important IS theories with the usefulness of the set of axioms in example 3.5. Each LLM applied the theories and axioms to three synthetic case studies and explained why the sets of theories and sets of axioms seemed useful when applied to the case studies. The three LLMs were asked to "vote" on whether the theories or axioms were more useful for each case study (3 LLMs x 3 case studies). The result was 7-2 in favor of the axioms, thus showing (in a truly strange way) that a set of axioms might be more practical than a set of theories regardless of how often Lewin's aphorism is repeated.

(3.7) Steps toward a theoretical foundation for the part of the IS field related to systems in organizations. A Delphi study in Becker et al. (2015) identified producing a theoretical foundation for the IS field as a grand challenge for the field. Preliminary efforts indicate that GenAI applied to aspects of WSP and a taxonomy of knowledge objects - KOs (e.g., concepts, generalizations, and methods) might generate meaningful progress in that direction. Information systems, projects, software development, etc., can all be viewed as work systems (see Figure 1). The basic approach applies GenAI to compile KOs of major types related to the nine elements of the work system framework, facets of those elements, and phases and subphases in the work system life cycle model. Preliminary efforts have

demonstrated GenAI's ability to identify and organize numerous KOs of different types but have not produced a practical, human-in-the-loop approach for refining lengthy lists of KOs to produce practical tools. Ideally, an iterative, GenAI-assisted compilation process would rely on humans in the loop to guide it in potentially useful directions and to evaluate interim results. That approach would focus on an essential part of the IS field (systems in organizations) and would provide a basis for further developments related to other important topics.

4 Conclusion

This paper emphasizes exploratory applications of GenAI that illustrate a new genre of IS research. That type of research has potential for producing ideas and tools that business and IT professionals might be able to apply to the challenges that they face. Those applications might occur through checklists, computerized analysis tools, or applications of LLMs or AI-based agents designed to use those ideas.

The above examples support the general notion that LLMs might be applied to IS research about basic concepts, generalizations, and methods. Such efforts would need to compensate carefully for LLM shortcomings such as imprecision of prompts, inconsistent responses to the same prompt, hallucinations, and limited understanding of contexts. Beyond the challenges of designing and performing that research, attempts to publish that type of research are likely to encounter skepticism among IS community members who are more comfortable with traditional research approaches. Even with those obstacles, this type of research could yield high impact in research and practice by expanding knowledge and methods for creating, describing, evaluating, and improving important work systems.

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